

THE INFLUENCE OF THERMAL AGEING ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF GREEN RUBBER COMPOSITE

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1 Introduction

Green composites can be tailored made to suit applications with desired properties by incorporating particulate natural filler into a rubber matrix. Natural rubber (NR) is a renewable natural resource derived from the latex of rubber tree. It can be prepared various rubber products from vulcanized rubber. Inorganic fillers which are widely used in vulcanized rubber composite such as glass fiber, mica, carbon black and silica are very relatively expensive compared to natural fibers. Thus, there is an increasing use of rubber composite filled with natural fibers for economic and environmental reasons. Natural fibers have advantages because of their renewable nature, low cost, plenty availability. In previous work, various natural fibers have been used as reinforcement in NR such as wood flour, rice husk, sisal, oil palm, flax and jute [1-4]. In this study, jute roving filled natural rubber green composite were prepared using hot compression molding technique. The optimization of jute roving length, fibers loading on mechanical and thermal aging properties were revealed.

2 Experimental

Natural rubber (NR) grade STR20 was supplied by Thai Hua Rubber Co. Ltd. Jute roving having an average diameter of 0.8 mm were supported by KIT, Japan. The fiber lengths of 5 cm and fiber loading of 10, 20, 30, 40, 50 and 60wt%, respectively, were used in this study. Moisture content of fiber was measured by Moisture Analyzer, Mettler Toledo, model HB43-S. The jute fiber was dried for 11 hrs at 100°C prior to being compounded with NR in a two roll mill. The fiber was milled at constant time for all composition. It was kept at 25°C for 24 hrs prior

to cure assessment on a Moving Die Rheometer, GOTECH, model GT-M2000. The vulcanization was carried out in compression molding technique under pressure of about 4 MPa, 160°C according to the optimum cure time obtained from rheometer data. The stress-strain properties of rubber composite were subjected to Instron Universal Testing Machine according to ASTM D412 at crosshead speed of 500 mm/min. The hardness was measured by the shore type A Durometer according to ASTM D2240. Thermal aging properties were measured by exposing the composite at 100°C for 22 hrs. Physical properties that is water absorption and morphological properties were also investigated.

3 Results and Discussion

Cure characteristics of fibers loading content into NR are represented in Table 1. It is shown that the torque value increased as fiber loading increased. The increase in the torque values from minimum “ M_L ” to the maximum “ M_H ” indicates that as more and fiber present into the rubber matrix, the mobility of the macromolecular chains of the rubber reduces resulting in more rigid vulcanizates. While, the cure time and scorch time was found to be independent of fiber loading. It is similar to previous report that is the rubber phase play a crucial role in the performance of based natural fiber composite [5].

The effect of fiber loading on mechanical properties in NR/jute green composite was observed. Typical stress-strain curve of NR/jute green composite is shown in Fig.1. Natural rubber inherently shows high strength due to strain-induced crystallization. When fiber is incorporated into NR, the regular arrangement of rubber molecules is difficult and hence the ability for crystallization is decrease. These were dependent on ageing

properties of the rubber composite. Tensile strength, % Elongation and Modulus before and after thermal ageing were shown in Fig.2-4. From Fig.2 it is clear that tensile strength increases up to 20wt% fiber loading and then declines. At lower level of fiber loading indicate a lack of adhesion between fiber and rubber. At 20 wt% fiber, it is a suitable content to participate in stress transfer. At high level, the increased in fibers leading to agglomeration and barrier a stress transfer. On the other hand, after ageing for 22 hrs at 100°C, the tensile strength is increases as fiber loading increase. These may be due to the better orientation of fiber. The elongation at break of rubber composite decreased with increasing fiber loading, as shown in Fig. 3. These were independent to thermal ageing. However, the increments of fiber loading resulting in dramatically increase in modulus of the composite in both conditions as shown in Fig.4.

4 Conclusions

The reinforcement of NR/jute green composite is acquired due to the naturally improved strength and modulus at fiber content higher than 40wt%, after thermal ageing. Before ageing, the optimum loading of fiber was found to be 20wt%.

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Table 1 Vulcanization characteristics of NR/jute green composites.

NR/Jute composite	M_H (dMn)	M_L (dNm)	M_H-M_L (dNm)	T_{C90} (min)	T_{S2} (min)	CRI(min^{-1})
90/10	47.55	1.05	46.50	5.05	1.06	25.06
80/20	56.70	1.14	55.56	5.40	1.12	23.36
70/30	64.45	1.15	63.30	5.09	1.12	25.18
60/40	86.76	1.67	85.09	5.29	1.15	24.15
50/50	94.52	1.84	92.68	6.03	1.21	20.74
40/60	138.80	5.64	133.16	6.35	1.26	19.64

$$\text{Cure time} = T_{C90}, \text{ Scorch time} = T_{S2}, \text{ Cure Rate Index} = 100/(T_{C90} - T_{S2})$$

Fig. 1 Stress-strain curve for NR/jute green composite with fiber loading.

Fig. 2 Effect of thermal ageing on tensile strength of NR/jute composite.

Fig. 3 Effect of thermal ageing on % elongation of NR/jute composite.

Fig. 4 Effect of thermal ageing on modulus of NR/jute composite.